

An X-Ray Investigation of the Crystals of Benzoin.

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Benzoin (Ph·CO·CHOH·Ph) was prepared by refluxing a mixture of benzaldehyde (25 g. Merck's Extra Pure), KCN (2.5 g. Kahlbaum's Extra Pure), rectified spirit (31.5 c.c.) and water (25. c.c.) for about an hour. By this method pure benzoin was obtained which gave well developed small crystals after three crystallisations from alcohol, m. p. 134° (Groth, m. p. 134°).

The crystals are found to grow $a\{100\}$, $c\{001\}$, and $\sigma\{20\bar{1}\}$ with end faces $\omega\{11\bar{1}\}$. They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and $a : b : c = 3.4397 : 1 : 1.8914$, $\beta = 106^\circ 50\frac{1}{2}'$ (cf. Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie," Vol. V., p. 199).

The crystals prepared as above were found to develop the $a\{100\}$, $c\{001\}$, $\sigma\{20\bar{1}\}$ and $\omega\{11\bar{1}\}$ faces and sometimes (101). They were examined by the rotating crystal method using k -copper radiations from a Shearer gas tube. The rotation photographs about the three axes (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) gave the following dimensions for the unit cell

$$a = 18.75 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 5.72 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 10.46 \text{ \AA}, \quad \beta = 106^\circ 50\frac{1}{2}'$$

A rotation photograph was also taken about an axis perpendicular to the b -axis in the (101) plane. The length of the axis was found to be 24.05 \AA which agrees with the calculated value 23.97 \AA. The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 3.28 : 1 : 1.83$ which agrees fairly well with that given above.

Rotation photograph.

FIG. 1.

About a -axis. $D = 5.07$ cm.

FIG. 2.

About b -axis. $D = 5.07$ cm.

FIG. 3.

About c -axis. $D = 5.07$ cm.

Oscillation photographs were taken about the *b* and *c*-axes at intervals of 15°. The spots appearing on the photographs were indexed by Bernal's method (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1910, **A** 113, 117). The following tables give a list of planes identified together with an eye estimation of their relative intensity for which the following notations have been employed :

V.s. = very strong, m.s. = medium strong, w.m. = weak medium, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak and v. w. = very weak.

TABLE I.

Axial planes.		Prism planes (hol).		Prism planes (okl).		Prism planes (hko).			
001	v. s.	...	201	s.	011	v. s.	110	v. s.	
002	s.	202	v. s.	202	m.	012	v. s.	210	s.
003	m. s.	203	s.	203	m.	013	s.	220	m.
004	m. s.	204	m.	...	...	021	m.	310	m. s.
200	v. s.	401	m.	401	v. s., s.	022	m.	410	m. s.
400	v. s., s.	402	w.	402	v. s.	023	w.	510	w. m., w.
600	m. s.	403	m. s.	403	w.			520	w.
1000	w. m.	404	m.	...	...			610	m.
		601	v. w.	601	m. s., m.			620	w. m.
		602	m.	602	m. s.			710	m. s., m.
		603	w. m.	...	...			720	w.
		...	...	604	m.			810	w. m., w.
		605	v. w.	605	w. m.				
		801	w.	...	...				
				802	m. s.				
				803	m.				
				804	m.				
				1001	w. m.				
				1003	w.				

TABLE II.

General planes.

111 v. s.	111 v. s.	312 m.	312 m.,w,m.	522 m.,w,m.	...	...
112 m. s.	112 m. s.	313 m. s.	313 w. m.	...	...	523 w.
113 w. m.	113 w. m.	314 w.,m.,w.	314 w.	611 m.	...	611 m. s.
121 s.,m,s.	121 s.,m,s.	321 w. m.	321 w.,m.,h.	612 m.	...	612m.
122 w. m.	122 w.	322 m.	...	614 m.	...	614 m. m.
123 w.	123 w.	324 } 423 } m.	323 v. w.	621 w. m.	...	621 w.
124 v. w.	...	411 s.	411 m. s.	...	...	622 m.,w,m
211 m.	211 m.	412 m.	412 w. m.	623 m.,w,m.	...	623 w. m.
212 m. s.	212 m.	413 m.	413 w. m.	711 w.	...	...
213 s.	213 m.	414 w. m.	414 w. m.	712 m.	...	712 w. m.
214 w.	214 m.	421 m.	421 w.	713 w. m.	...	713 w.,m.,w.
221 m.	221 s.	422 m. s.	422 m.	...	...	715 v. w.
222 m. s.	222 v. w.	423 w.,m.,w.	423 m.	721 w.	...	721 w. m.
223 w.	223 v. w.	424 m.	...	...	...	722 w. m.
224 } 324 } w.	...	512 m. s.	512 m.	811 m.	...	811 m.
311 s.	311 m.	513 w.	...	812 m.	...	812 w.
		521 w. m.	521 w. m.	813 m.	...	813 m.
				821 w.	...	...
				913 w. m.	...	913 w.

It will be seen from the above list of planes that (hol) planes are halved when h is odd. Further (oko) planes have not appeared at all. This shows that these planes are very weakly reflecting. It is, therefore, probable that (oro) is halved and (o2o) being very weak has not appeared. The crystals may, therefore, belong to the space group C_{2h}^2 (cf. Astbury and Yardley, *Phil. Trans.*, 1924, **A**, 224, 221).

This is more likely since a large number of organic crystals belonging to the monoclinic prismatic class belong to this space group. The number of molecules in the unit cell required by the space group is four and that calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the density of the crystals (found to be = 1.310) is

$$n = \frac{abc \sin \beta \times \rho}{M \times 1.66} = 3.997 = 4 \text{ (approx.)}$$

This shows that the molecules in the cell are asymmetric.

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